

KARRALI TRIGONOMETRIK INTEGRALLAR

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ABSTRACT

Bu maqolada karrali trigonometrik integrallar uchun bir nechta baholarni olamiz. Dastlab, eksponential ko'phad bo'lgan holda karrali trigonometrik integrallar uchun F(x) funksiyalar uchun J integrallarning aniq baholarini isbotlaymiz.

Quyidagi ko'rinishdagi integral

$$J = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r,$$

trigonometrik integral deyiladi, bu yerda F(x1, ..., xr)-r ta x1, ..., xr o'zgaruvchilarning haqiqiy funksiyasi. Bunday funksiyalar analitik sonlar nazariyasida, funksiyalar nazariyasida, matematik fizikada, ehtimollar nazariyasida va matematik statistika nazariyasida uchraydi. J ga bog'liq asosiy masalalardan biri uning modulining yuqori chegarasini topish masalasidir. Buning uchun quyidagi yordamchi teorema va lemmalarni keltiramiz.

Lemma 1. Faraz qilaylik, f(x) = alpha_n x^n + ... + alpha_1 x bunda alpha_n, ..., alpha_1 -haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib, ulardan moduli eng kattasini alpha orqali belgilaymiz. U holda

$$I = \int_0^1 f(x) \exp\{2\pi i f(x)\} dx$$

integral uchun

$$|I| \leq \min(1, 32\alpha^{-1/n})$$

tengsizlik o'rinli.

Teorema 1. Faraz qilaylik, alpha = max_{0 <= t_1, ..., t_r <= n} |alpha(t_1, ..., t_r)|, alpha(0, ..., 0) = 0,

$$I_r = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r, \quad F(x_1, \dots, x_r) = \sum_{t_1=0}^n \dots \sum_{t_r=0}^n \alpha(t_1, \dots, t_r) x_1^{t_1} \dots x_r^{t_r}$$

bo'lsin, bunda

U holda quyidagi baho o'rinli:

$$|I_r| \leq \min(1, 32^r \alpha^{-1/n} \ln^{r-1}(\alpha + 2))$$

Isbot. $r=1$ uchun teorema o'rinli (1-lemmaga qarang). Ko'phadning o'zgaruvchilari soni bo'yicha induksiyaning qo'llaymiz. Faraz qilaylik, teorema $r-1$ o'zgaruvchi uchun o'rinli bo'lsin. Uning r o'zgaruvchi uchun o'rinli ekanligini isbotlaymiz. Umumiylikka zarar yetkazmasdan absolyut qiymat bo'yicha eng katta koeffitsenti noldan farqli darajali x_1 o'zgaruvchiga tegishli bo'lsin deylik. $\alpha = |\alpha(s_1, \dots, s_r)|$ bo'lsin, u holda $s_1 > 0$ bo'ladi.

$$F(x_1, \dots, x_r) = \sum_{t_1=0}^n \dots \sum_{t_{r-1}=0}^n x_1^{t_1} \dots x_{r-1}^{t_{r-1}} \varphi_{t_1, \dots, t_{r-1}}(x_r), \quad t = [\ln(\alpha + 1)] + 1, \quad E_0 = \{x_r \mid |\varphi_{s_1, \dots, s_{r-1}}(x_r)| \leq 1\},$$
$$E_k = \{x_r \mid \alpha^{(k-1)/t} < |\varphi_{s_1, \dots, s_{r-1}}(x_r)| < \alpha^{k/t}\}, \quad k = \overline{1, t-1}, \quad E_t = \{x_r \mid \alpha^{(t-1)/t} < |\varphi_{s_1, \dots, s_{r-1}}(x_r)|\}$$
 deylik.

E_k to'plamga tegishli bo'lgan intervallarning uzunligini $mes E_k$ orqali belgilaymiz. 1-lemmada quyidagi baho isbotlangan edi:

$$mes \{x \mid |f(x)| < A\} \leq 4e(A\alpha^{-1})^{1/n}$$

Shuning uchun $mes E_k \leq 4e\alpha^{-(t+k)/(m)}$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, t$ tengsizlikga egamiz.

I_r integral uchun

$$|I_r| \leq mes E_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{t-1} mes E_k \max_{x_r \in E_k} \left| \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_{r-1} \right| + \max_{x_r \in E_t} \left| \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_{r-1} \right|$$

tengsizlik o'rinli. Induksiya faraziga ko'ra

$$\max_{x_r \in E_k} \left| \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_{r-1} \right| \leq \min(1, 32^{r-1} \alpha^{-(k-1)/(m)} \ln^{r-2}(\alpha + 2))$$

bo'ladi. Bundan

$$|I_r| \leq 4e\alpha^{-1/n} + \sum_{k=1}^{t-1} 4e\alpha^{-(t+k)/(m)} 32^{r-1} \alpha^{-(k-1)/(m)} \ln^{(r-2)}(\alpha + 2) + 32^{r-1} \alpha^{-(t-1)/(m)} \ln^{r-2}(\alpha + 2) \leq 32^r \alpha^{-1/n} \ln^{r-1}(\alpha + 2)$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Bundan tashqari $|I_r| \leq 1$ oddiy tengsizlikning bajarilishi ma'lum. Bu bahoni oldingisiga birlashtirib lemmaning tasdiqini hosil qilamiz.

Quyidagi lemma olingan bahoning aniqligini ko'rsatadi.

Lemma 2. Faraz qilaylik, $\alpha > 1$

$$I_r(\alpha) = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i \alpha x_1^n, \dots, x_r^n\} dx_1 \dots dx_r$$

bo'lsin. U holda I_r uchun quyidan

$$|I_r(\alpha)| \geq \frac{1}{2\pi n^r (r-1)!} \alpha^{-1/n} (\ln \alpha)^{r-1}$$

baho o'rinli.

Isbot. Dastlab

$$I_r(\alpha) = \frac{(-1)^{r-1}}{(r-1)!} \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i \alpha x^n\} (\ln x)^{r-1} dx$$

formulaning o'rinli ekanligini ko'rsatamiz. Uni induksiya yordamida isbotlaymiz. $r = 1$ uchun formula o'rinli. $r - 1$ uchun to'g'ri deb faraz qilamiz.

r uchun isbot qilaylik. Farazga ko'ra

$$I_r(\alpha) = \int_0^1 I_r(\alpha x^n) dx = \int_0^1 \frac{(-1)^{r-2}}{(r-2)!} \left(\int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i \alpha x^n y^n\} (\ln y)^{r-2} dy \right) dx$$

bo'ladi. $z = xy$ almashtirishdan so'ng

$$I_r(\alpha) = \frac{(-1)^{r-2}}{(r-2)!} \int_0^1 \frac{dx}{x} \int_0^x \exp\{2\pi i \alpha z^n\} (\ln z - \ln x)^{r-2} dz$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Oxirgi integralni bo'laklab integrallaylik:

$$I_r(\alpha) = \frac{(-1)^{r-2}}{(r-2)!} \int_0^1 (d \ln x) \int_0^x \exp\{2\pi i \alpha z^n\} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{r-2} (-1)^k \binom{r-2}{k} (\ln x)^k (\ln z)^{r-2-k} \right) dz = \frac{(-1)^{r-2}}{(r-2)!} \times$$

$$\times \sum_{k=0}^{r-2} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+1} \binom{r-2}{k} \int_0^1 (d \ln x)^{k+1} \int_0^x \exp\{2\pi i \alpha z^n\} (\ln z)^{r-2-k} dz = \frac{(-1)^{r-1}}{(r-2)!} \sum_{k=0}^{r-2} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+1} \binom{r-2}{k} \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i \alpha z^n\} \times$$

$$\times (\ln z)^{r-1} dz$$

$$\frac{1}{r-1} \sum_{k=0}^{r-2} \frac{(-1)^k}{k+1} (r-1) \binom{r-2}{k} = \frac{1}{r-1}$$

ekanligidan, buning r o'zgaruvchi uchun ham to'g'riligi kelib chiqadi. $\alpha > 1$ da $|I_r(\alpha)|$ ni quyidan baholaymiz. $J = \text{Im}(I_r(\alpha))$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$J = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_0^1 \sin(2\pi \alpha y^n) \left(\ln \frac{1}{y} \right)^{r-1} dy = \frac{1}{n^r (r-1)!} \int_0^1 \sin(2\pi \alpha z) \left(\ln \frac{1}{z} \right)^{r-1} z^{-1+1/n} dz =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\pi \alpha n^r (r-1)!} \int_0^1 \left(\ln \frac{1}{z} \right)^{r-1} z^{-1+1/n} d(\sin^2(\pi \alpha z)) = -\frac{1}{\pi \alpha n^r (r-1)!} \int_0^1 \sin^2(\pi \alpha z) d \left(\left(\ln \frac{1}{z} \right)^{r-1} z^{-1+1/n} \right)$$

ga ega bo'lamiz. Undan tashqari

$$J = -\frac{1}{\pi \alpha n^r (r-1)!} \int_{1/(2\alpha)}^{1+1/(2\alpha)} \cos^2(\pi \alpha z) d \left(\left(\ln \frac{1}{z-1/(2\alpha)} \right)^{r-1} (z-1/(2\alpha))^{-1+1/n} \right)$$

$$-\frac{d}{dz} \left(\left(\ln \frac{1}{z} \right)^{r-1} z^{-1+1/n} \right) \geq 0 \quad (0 < z < 1)$$

monoton kamayuvchi funksiya ekanligidan, J uchun olingan ifodalarni yig'sak.

$$2J > -\frac{1}{\pi \alpha n^r (r-1)!} \int_{1/\alpha}^1 d\left(\left(\frac{\ln \frac{1}{z}}{z}\right)^{r-1} z^{-1+1/n}\right) = \frac{1}{\pi n^r (r-1)!} \alpha^{-1/n} (\ln \alpha)^{r-1}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Shunday qilib,

$$|I_r(\alpha)| \geq J \geq \frac{1}{2\pi n^r (r-1)!} \alpha^{-1/n} (\ln \alpha)^{r-1}$$

Lemma isbot bo'ldi.

Teorema 2. Faraz qilaylik, $\alpha = \max_{t_1, \dots, t_r} |\alpha(t_1, \dots, t_r)|$, $\alpha(0, \dots, 0) = 0$,

$$I_r = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r$$

bo'lsin,

$$F(x_1, \dots, x_r) = \sum_{t_1=0}^{n_1} \dots \sum_{t_r=0}^{n_r} \alpha(t_1, \dots, t_r) x_1^{t_1} \dots x_r^{t_r}$$

bunda . U holda I_r integral uchun quyidagi baho o'rinli

$$|I_r| \leq \min(1, 32^r \alpha^{-1/n} \ln^{r-1}(\alpha + 2))$$

$$\text{bunda } n = \max(n_1, \dots, n_r)$$

Isbot. $F(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ ko'phadni quyidagi ko'rinishda yozish mumkin.

$$F(x_1, \dots, x_r) = \sum_{t_1=0}^n \dots \sum_{t_r=0}^n \beta(t_1, \dots, t_r) x_1^{t_1} \dots x_r^{t_r}$$

, bu yerda $\beta(t_1, \dots, t_r)$ koeffitsientlar

$$\beta(t_1, \dots, t_r) = \begin{cases} \alpha(t_1, \dots, t_r) & \text{agar } 0 \leq t_1 \leq n_1, \dots, 0 \leq t_r \leq n_r \text{ bo'lsa} \\ 0 & \text{aks holda} \end{cases}$$

tengliklar bilan aniqlanadi. Faraz qilaylik, $\beta = \max_{0 \leq t_1, \dots, t_r \leq n} |\beta(t_1, \dots, t_r)|$ bo'lsin. U holda osongina ko'rish mumkinki, $\beta = \alpha$ tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi. Endi I_r ni 1.3-teoremaga ko'ra baholaymiz. Quyidagi

$$|I_r| \leq \min(1, 32^r \beta^{-1/n} \ln^{r-1}(\beta + 2)) = \min(1, 32^r \alpha^{-1/n} \ln^{r-1}(\alpha + 2))$$

ga ega bo'lamiz. Shuni isbotlash talab qilingan edi.

Teorema 3. Faraz qilaylik, $k_1, \dots, k_r$ -natural sonlar uchun $k = k_1 + \dots + k_r$, $v = \frac{1}{k}$, $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r$ -haqiqiy sonlar va barcha $(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ ($0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1$) nuqtalar uchun

$$\left| \frac{\partial^k f(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial x_1^{k_1} \dots \partial x_r^{k_r}} \right| > H$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'lsin.

Faraz qilaylik, $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ yo'nalish uchun shunday $v = \binom{k+r-1}{r-1}$ topilsinki, u

a) $0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1$ kubga qarashli va ixtiyoriy oraliqdan olingan v ning $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$

$$\left. \frac{\partial^k f(x_1 + \alpha_1 t, \dots, x_2 + \alpha_2)}{\partial t^k} \right|_{t=0}$$

yo'nalishli hosilaning monotonlik oraliqlari soni m dan oshmasin.

b) $M = \left(\frac{k!}{s_1! \dots s_r!} \alpha_1^{s_1} \dots \alpha_r^{s_r} \right)$, (bunda, $0 \leq s_1, \dots, s_r \leq k$, $k = s_1 + \dots + s_r$ va $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ vektorlar

ko'rsatilgan v vektorlar bo'yicha o'zgaradi) matrisa determinantining moduli $R > 0$ dan oshmasin, va M matrisa elementlari har birining algebraik to'ldiruvchisi modul bo'yicha $T > 0$ dan oshmasin. U holda

$$J = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i f(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r$$

integral uchun

$$|J| \leq 6k v^{2+v} m T^v R^{-v} H^{-v}$$

baho o'rinli.

Isbot. Har bir $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ yo'nalish uchun

$$\left. \frac{\partial^k f(x_1 + \alpha_1 t, \dots, x_2 + \alpha_2)}{\partial t^k} \right|_{t=0} = \sum_{\substack{s_1=0 \\ \dots \\ s_r=0 \\ s_1+\dots+s_r=k}}^k \dots \sum^k \frac{k!}{s_1! \dots s_r!} \alpha_1^{s_1} \dots \alpha_r^{s_r} \frac{\partial^k f(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial x_1^{s_1} \dots \partial x_r^{s_r}}$$

tenglikka egamiz. Ularni $\frac{\partial^k f(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial x_1^{s_1} \dots \partial x_r^{s_r}}$ noma'lumlar bo'yicha chiziqli tenglamalar

$$\text{sistemi sifatida qarab, } \frac{\partial^k f(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial x_1^{k_1} \dots \partial x_r^{k_r}} = \sum_{(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)} \dots \sum c(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r) \left. \frac{\partial^k f(x_1 + \alpha_1 t, \dots, x_2 + \alpha_2)}{\partial t^k} \right|_{t=0}$$

larni topamiz, bunda $\sum_{(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)} \dots \sum$ -teorema shartlaridan aniqlangan barcha $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$

yo'nalishlar bo'yicha yig'indini bildiradi va $|c(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)|$ koefitsientlar TR^{-1} dan oshmaydi. Har

bir $(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ ($0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1$) nuqta uchun $\left| \frac{\partial^k f(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial x_1^{k_1} \dots \partial x_r^{k_r}} \right| > H$ tengsizlik bajarilgani sababli

ixtiyoriy $(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ nuqta uchun shunday $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ yo'nalish topiladiki, unda

$$\left| \frac{\partial^k f(x_1 + \alpha_1 t, \dots, x_2 + \alpha_2)}{\partial t^k} \right|_{t=0} > v^{-1} T^{-1} R H$$

tengsizlik bajariladi. $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ yo'nalishni biror usul yordamida tartiblaymiz va $\Omega = \{(x_1, \dots, x_r) | 0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1\}$ kubni o'zaro kesishmaydigan $\Omega_s (s=1, \dots, v)$ sohalarga ajratamiz.

Birinchi Ω_1 sohaga birinchi yo'nalish bo'yicha k -tartibli hosilasi $v^{-1} T^{-1} R H$ dan katta bo'lgan barcha $(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ nuqtalarni joylashtiramiz;

Ikkinchi Ω_2 sohaga moduli ikkinchi yo'nalish bo'yicha k -tartibli hosilasi shu qiymatdan katta va 1-sohaga kirmaydigan nuqtalarni joylashtiramiz;

Uchinchisiga uchinchi yo'nalish bo'yicha k -tartibli hosilasining moduli $v^{-1}T^{-1}RH$ dan katta va 1- hamda 2- sohaga kirmaydigan barcha nuqtalarni joylashtiramiz va hokazo.(ayrim Ω_s sohalar bo'sh bo'lishi ham mumkin).

Har bir oraliqda Ω_s to'plamga tegishli s -yo'nalishga parallel sm dan ko'p bo'lmagan oraliqlar topilishi mumkin. Haqiqatan ham, har bir oraliq yo'nalishi $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ bo'lgan ixtiyoriy v ga parallel, Ω_1 ga tegishli va teorema shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi oraliqlar soni m dan oshmaydi. Yasashga ko'ra Ω_2 to'plam har bir oraliqda ixtiyoriy v yo'nalishga parallel, ikkinchisidan boshlab, Ω_2 ga tegishli $2m$ dan oshmaydigan oraliqlar mavjud va hokazo. J integralni quyidagicha yozaylik $J = J_1 + \dots + J_v$ bunda

$$J_s = \int_{\Omega_s} \dots \int \exp\{2\pi i f(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r$$

J_s integralni baholaymiz. Chiziqli ortogonal almashtirish kiritaylik, ya'ni, y_1 o'qni s inchi $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ vektorga parallel yo'naltiramiz, qolgan $y_2, \dots, y_r$ koordinata o'qlarini shunday tanlaymizki, $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_r$ koordinatalar sistemasi ortogonal va $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r$ koordinatalar sistemasi bilan bir xil orientirlangan bo'lsin.

Ω_s soha bu almashtirishdan so'ng Ω^s ga o'tadi va $f(x_1, \dots, x_r) = f_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)$ o'rinli bo'ladi. Har bir tayinlangan $(y_2, \dots, y_r)$ nuqtani shunday y_1 lar uchun $T(s; y_2, \dots, y_r)$ bilan ifodalaymizki, bunda $(y_1, \dots, y_r)$ nuqta Ω^s ga tegishli bo'lsin. $T(s; y_2, \dots, y_r)$ to'plam sm dan ko'p bo'lmagan oraliqlardan tashkil topgan. Ω^s ga tegishli bo'lgan $(y_1, \dots, y_r)$ nuqtaning $y_2, \dots, y_r$ o'zgaruvchilarining o'zgarish sohasini ω_s orqali belgilaymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} |J_s| &= \left| \int_{\omega_s} \dots \int_{T(s; y_2, \dots, y_r)} \exp\{2\pi i f_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)\} dy_1 \dots dy_r \right| \leq \int_{\omega_s} \dots \int_{T(s; y_2, \dots, y_r)} \left| \exp\{2\pi i f_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)\} dy_1 \right| dy_2 \dots dy_r \leq \\ &\leq \left| \int_{T(s; y_2^{(0)}, \dots, y_r^{(0)})} \exp\{2\pi i f_1(y_1, y_2^{(0)}, \dots, y_r^{(0)})\} dy_1 \right| \int_{\omega_s} \dots \int dy_2 \dots dy_r \end{aligned}$$

bunda $(y_2^{(0)}, \dots, y_r^{(0)})$ nuqta $\left| \int_{T(s; y_2, \dots, y_r)} \exp\{2\pi i f_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)\} dy_1 \right|$ funksiyaning maksimum nuqtasi.

$f_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)$ dan y_1 bo'yicha olingan k -tartibli hosila $v^{-1}T^{-1}RH$ dan katta ekanligidan va bir o'zgaruvchili funksiyadan k -tartibli olingan hosilaning bahosidan (1.2-lemmadan) quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$|J_s| \leq 6skv^v mT^v R^{-v} H^{-v}$$

$|J_s|$ uchun baholarni yig'sak,

$$|J| = |J_1| + \dots + |J_v| \leq \sum_{s=1}^v 6skv^v mT^v R^{-v} H^{-v} \leq 6kv^{v+2} mT^v R^{-v} H^{-v}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Teorema isbot bo'ldi.

$$\left| \frac{\partial^k F(x_1, \dots, x_r)}{\partial l^k} \right| > A > 0$$

Natija.1. Faraz qilaylik, biror l yo'nalish bo'yicha tengsizlik

o'rinli bo'lsin va $F(x_1, \dots, x_r)$ funksiya 1.5-teoremaning shartlarini qanoatlantirsin, hamda $G(x_1, \dots, x_r) \quad 0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1$ kubda yotuvchi va l ga parallel oraliqda bo'lakli monoton va bo'lakli uzluksiz bo'lib, $|G(x_1, \dots, x_r)| \leq H$ shartni qanoatlantirsin. U holda

$$J = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 G(x_1, \dots, x_r) \exp\{2\pi i F(x_1, \dots, x_r)\} dx_1 \dots dx_r$$

integral uchun

$$|J| \ll HA^{-1/k}$$

baho o'rinli.

Isbot. O'zgaruvchilarda chiziqli ortogonal almashtirish qilaylik (y_1 o'qni l ga parallel qilib yo'naltiraylik, qolganlarini esa birinchi koordinata sistemasi bilan yo'nalishdosh qilib yasaymiz). $0 \leq x_1, \dots, x_r \leq 1$ birlik kub Ω sohaga o'tadi, va $G(x_1, \dots, x_r) = G_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)$, $F(x_1, \dots, x_r) = F_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)$.

$$J = \int_{\Omega} \dots \int G_1(y_1, \dots, y_r) \exp\{2\pi i F_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)\} dy_1 \dots dy_r$$

ga egamiz.

Tayinlangan $y_2, \dots, y_r$ larni Ω ga tegishli bo'lgan $(y_1, \dots, y_r)$ nuqtalar to'plami $T(y_2, \dots, y_r)$ orqali belgilaymiz. $y_2, \dots, y_r$ larning o'zgarish sohasini ω bilan belgilaymiz. y_1 bo'yicha bo'laklab integrallasak;

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \int_{\omega} \dots \int \left(\int_{T(y_2, \dots, y_r)} G_1(y_1, \dots, y_r) \exp\{2\pi i F_1(y_1, \dots, y_r)\} dy_1 \right) dy_2 \dots dy_r = \\ &= \int_{\omega} \dots \int \left(\int_{T(y_2, \dots, y_r)} G_1(y_1, \dots, y_r) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \left(\int_0^{y_1} \exp\{2\pi i F_1(\xi_1, y_2, \dots, y_r)\} d\xi_1 \right) dy_1 \right) dy_2 \dots dy_r \\ &= \int_{\omega} \dots \int \left(\int_0^1 \exp\{2\pi i F_1(\xi_1, y_2, \dots, y_r)\} d\xi_1 \right) G_1(1, y_2, \dots, y_r) dy_2 \dots dy_r - \\ &- \int_{\omega} \dots \int \left(\int_{T(y_2, \dots, y_r)} \left(\int_0^{y_1} \exp\{2\pi i F_1(\xi_1, y_2, \dots, y_r)\} d\xi_1 \right) G_1(y_1, \dots, y_r) dy_1 \right) dy_2 \dots dy_r \end{aligned}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. 3-teoremaga ko'ra integralni baholasak

$$\left| \int_0^{y_1} \exp\{2\pi i F_1(\xi_1, y_2, \dots, y_r)\} d\xi_1 \right| \ll A^{-1/k}$$

natijada talab qilingan baho kelib chiqadi. Natija isbot bo'ldi.

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